

Are quark-doublets different?

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Quarks are fermions, hence must obey the Pauli Exclusion Principle; when confined some feature must exist to produce different quantum states when identical quarks are involved. Yet current assessments [1] do not show any variation in quantum numbers for a quark in a bound state with its double; instead, QCD invented 'color' as a fix-up.

In nucleons, composed of up and down quarks as {udd} for the Neutron, and P ~ {uud} for the Proton, repeated quarks cannot have identical quantum states, as is required of fermions. One option would be: N ~ {u₁d₁d₂} and P ~ {u₁u₂d₂} – although as yet unconfirmed.

This idea lends some simplicity to decay schematics; in Fermi beta decay

$$N \Rightarrow P + e^- + \bar{\nu}_e$$

the proposed transition scheme

shows up-quark **u₁** and down-quark **d₂** remaining unchanged, while down-quark **d₁** would become up-quark **u₂**. The emitted electron serves to preserve charge, as obviously

$$\text{charge}(e^-) + \text{charge}(u_2) = \text{charge}(d_1)$$

In the **V-A** theory [2], beta decay is actually produced through quark transition:

$$d_1 \Rightarrow u_2 + e^- + \bar{\nu}_e$$

A more useful decay scheme producing the same eventual outcome is shown below; up-quark **u₁** would remain unchanged, down-quark **d₁** would trade places with down-quark **d₂**, while down-quark **d₂** would now become up-quark **u₂**.

The quark transition producing this result is

$$d_2 \Rightarrow u_2 + e^- + \bar{\nu}_e$$

This second scheme links up nicely with the 'particle is a matrix' idea explored previously [3]; the six 3x3 permutation matrices execute the analogy this time:

$$\pi_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \quad \pi_2 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad \pi_3 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \quad \pi_4 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad \pi_5 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad \pi_6 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

The neutron triplet $\{u_1 d_1 d_2\}$ can be 'positioned' on the 1's inside any given permutation matrix in $3! = 6$ ways, or 36 ways total; the same for the proton triplet $\{u_1 u_2 d_2\}$. However, far fewer options are available when exactly one entry is the same for a pair of permutations. The table below shows the useful pairings, with (row, column) entries where the 'constant' u_1 quark would fit.

	π_2	π_3	π_4
π_1	2,2	3,3	1,1
π_5	3,1	1,2	2,3
π_6	1,3	2,1	3,2

The pairings

$$\begin{array}{lll} \{\pi_1, \pi_2\} & \{\pi_1, \pi_3\} & \{\pi_1, \pi_4\} \\ \{\pi_5, \pi_2\} & \{\pi_5, \pi_3\} & \{\pi_5, \pi_4\} \\ \{\pi_6, \pi_2\} & \{\pi_6, \pi_3\} & \{\pi_6, \pi_4\} \end{array}$$

can accommodate any nucleon duo, as either $\{N, P\}$ (used hereon) or $\{P, N\}$. For example, the assignments $\{\pi_5, \pi_3\}$ as $\{N_5, P_3\}$ would yield

$$N_5 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & u_1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & d_2 \\ d_1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad P_3 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & u_1 & 0 \\ u_2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & d_2 \end{pmatrix}$$

The full assignment table follows; index numbering to match permutations with nucleons. Right below it is the Cayley table for permutations, to be used presently.

		P_2	P_3	P_4
		π_2	π_3	π_4
N_1	π_1	2,2	3,3	1,1
N_5	π_5	3,1	1,2	2,3
N_6	π_6	1,3	2,1	3,2

*	π_2	π_3	π_4	π_5	π_6
π_2	π_1	π_6	π_5	π_4	π_3
π_3	π_5	π_1	π_6	π_2	π_4
π_4	π_6	π_5	π_1	π_3	π_2
π_6	π_4	π_2	π_3	π_1	π_5
π_5	π_3	π_4	π_2	π_6	π_1

The permutations leading to doubly stochastic transition agents are in red.

$$\pi_1 \pi_2 = \pi_2 \quad \pi_1 \pi_3 = \pi_3 \quad \pi_1 \pi_4 = \pi_4$$

$$\pi_5 \pi_4 = \pi_2 \quad \pi_5 \pi_2 = \pi_3 \quad \pi_5 \pi_3 = \pi_4$$

$$\pi_6 \pi_3 = \pi_2 \quad \pi_6 \pi_4 = \pi_3 \quad \pi_6 \pi_2 = \pi_4$$

Therefore, some permutation π_k right-multiplies 'neutrons' from the set $\{\pi_1, \pi_5, \pi_6\}$ to generate the resulting 'protons' in the set $\{\pi_2, \pi_3, \pi_4\}$, albeit triply redundantly. It is here that quark-mixing strategies previously detailed in [4] lead naturally to a mechanism yielding transition probabilities of neutron-to-proton decay. This family of doubly stochastic matrices

M_{kj} 'pinned' on π_k is paired with 'neutrons' from the above table to yield transition probabilities for decay to 'protons'. Thus

$$M_{kj}(\theta) = c^2\pi_k + s^2\pi_j$$

where as usual $c = \cos(\theta)$ and $s = \sin(\theta)$, for some angle θ . All nine options with ensuing outcomes are listed below; 'neutrons' in blue highlights, 'protons' in yellow.

$$M_{21}(\theta) = c^2\pi_2 + s^2\pi_1 \Rightarrow \pi_1 M_{21}(\theta) = c^2\pi_2 + s^2\pi_1$$

$$M_{45}(\theta) = c^2\pi_4 + s^2\pi_5 \Rightarrow \pi_5 M_{45}(\theta) = c^2\pi_5\pi_4 + s^2\pi_5^2 = c^2\pi_2 + s^2\pi_6$$

$$M_{36}(\theta) = c^2\pi_3 + s^2\pi_6 \Rightarrow \pi_6 M_{36}(\theta) = c^2\pi_6\pi_3 + s^2\pi_6^2 = c^2\pi_2 + s^2\pi_5$$

$$M_{31}(\theta) = c^2\pi_3 + s^2\pi_1 \Rightarrow \pi_1 M_{31}(\theta) = c^2\pi_3 + s^2\pi_1$$

$$M_{25}(\theta) = c^2\pi_2 + s^2\pi_5 \Rightarrow \pi_5 M_{25}(\theta) = c^2\pi_5\pi_2 + s^2\pi_5^2 = c^2\pi_3 + s^2\pi_6$$

$$M_{46}(\theta) = c^2\pi_4 + s^2\pi_6 \Rightarrow \pi_6 M_{46}(\theta) = c^2\pi_6\pi_4 + s^2\pi_6^2 = c^2\pi_3 + s^2\pi_5$$

$$M_{41}(\theta) = c^2\pi_4 + s^2\pi_1 \Rightarrow \pi_1 M_{41}(\theta) = c^2\pi_4 + s^2\pi_1$$

$$M_{35}(\theta) = c^2\pi_3 + s^2\pi_5 \Rightarrow \pi_5 M_{35}(\theta) = c^2\pi_5\pi_3 + s^2\pi_5^2 = c^2\pi_4 + s^2\pi_6$$

$$M_{26}(\theta) = c^2\pi_2 + s^2\pi_6 \Rightarrow \pi_6 M_{26}(\theta) = c^2\pi_6\pi_2 + s^2\pi_6^2 = c^2\pi_4 + s^2\pi_5$$

Estimation with the Cabibbo angle $\theta = 13.04^\circ = .2276$ rad yielded reasonable results; one example of neutron-decay outcome is compared below as matrices.

$$N_5 M_{25}(\theta) \quad P_3$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & .949u_1 & .051u_1 \\ d_2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & .051d_1 & .949d_1 \end{pmatrix} \sim \begin{pmatrix} 0 & u_1 & 0 \\ u_2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & d_2 \end{pmatrix}$$

Down-quark d_2 is indeed positioned correctly as up-quark u_2 in proton P_3 , but up-quark u_1 and down-quark d_1 show small probability errors (in yellow), perhaps due to the unphysical assumptions made herein. However, mass values (in MeV/c²) for $u_1 = 2.3$, $d_1 = 4.8$, and $e^- = .511$ do lead to a curious fact: when used as mass-weights the errors yield

$$.051*2.3(u_1) + .051*4.8(d_1) = .362(\sim e^-)$$

within range of the electron mass; so, the proposed mechanism for beta-decay seems numerically productive, if incomplete – no neutrinos emerged.

References

- [1] Wikipedia article on 'Quarks'.
- [2] K. Moriyasu, 'An elementary primer for gauge theory', World Scientific, 1983.
- [3] A. Cusmariu, 'A mesonic Ninefold Way', Zenodo.org/records/8250158, 2023.
- [4] A. Cusmariu, 'Elementary particle mixings as convex sums of permutations', Zenodo.org/records/10104280, 2023.